

Research Article

LANGUAGE ASPECTS OF NETIZEN COMMUNICATION

Morphology

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Adelina Hoxhaj

Master of Science (MSc). Department of English Language and Literature.
Faculty of Philology. State University of Tetovo. North Macedonia.
Republic of Kosovo.

Abstract

The goal of the linguistic and cultural study of Internet communication is to define the particulars of communication within a given group or environment, identify the formulas that are most frequently used for speech etiquette and communication features in general, characterize the cultural dominants of the relevant community in the form of concepts as units of the mental sphere, and pinpoint the appropriate case texts for this lingoculture. Internet communication, which is viewed as a cognitive-semantic phenomena, is linked to a variety of models of representation of communication in consciousness, including frames, scripts, mental schemes, cogniotips, addresses, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Kubryakova (2012), who supports a cognitive-semantic approach to online communication, characterizes it as a cognitive process aimed at real speech production, the creation of a speech work, but the text is considered to be the final result of the process of communication activity, which as a result takes a certain completed fixed form. Kubryakova (2012) emphasizes the engagement of communication partners, highlighting in particular the knowledge, ideas, attitudes, and situation assessments that are communicated by them after confirming that Internet communication is targeted. It is suggestive that the particulars of employing different linguistic tools in online communication lend the text a certain static or dynamic, controllability or uncontrol, integrity or instantaneity, length or repeatability, causation or spontaneity.

There are sociolinguistic interpretations of the notions presented in addition to the different linguistic ones. Thus, structuralists like Kristeva (2015) points out that ‘communication methods entirely predetermine and are frequently motivated by human goals (to music, sports, literature, tourism, etc.)’. In fact, the definition of Internet communication's connection with any particular restricted field of knowledge should be taken into account as a sign of the communicative originality of the subject of social activity, and this subject may be particular, collective, or even abstract.

Each distinct language consists of a set of components whose connections, contrasts, and interconnections are expressed in speech in a unique way. The addressee constructs the macrostructure, which the researcher understands as a broad description of the communication's core content, during the comprehension process. According to the scientist, the macrostructure of communication, which is a complete text, reflects the structure of long-term memory and

summarizes the information that is retained for a considerable amount of time in the memories of people who have read and/or heard a specific text that is a crucial component of this type of communication.

Internet communication can be defined as a particular form of interpersonal cognitive process that involves people communicating with one another through the global Internet. It is addressed as direct communication (face-to-face or tête-à-tête) between one chatter participant and another, as well as in the appeal of one Internet text author to a large audience of other users who use the Internet to discuss topics that are important to them.

It is vital to investigate the netizen as an equal participant in a speech act because of the emphasis of modern linguistics toward the study of the communicative features of language. The initiator of an online message is advised to choose language tools, including specialized and non-specialized ones, combine them, and create addressed statements that are characteristic of or acceptable for a particular type of Internet communication, taking into account the social status and formation of the netizen (i.e., recipient of information).

The environment in which a netizen's language can be expressed can typically be defined as the orientation of Internet communication related to the transfer of one or more pieces of information from one netizen to another, taking into account their sympathies and antipathies (in music, sports, literature, tourism, etc.).

Each distinct form of Internet communication creates signals of aesthetic, philosophical, ethical, etc. information structured in a particular way to encourage textual and intertextual associations and control how the netizen perceives the text, resulting in a variety of "codes" of interpretation of hidden meanings as well as negative or positive evaluative emotions in his mind. In this regard, we can concur with E. N. Litvin (2011), who holds that specific patterns of a typical nature, objective factors of text formation, and the aggregate structure of this text all contribute to the recipient of an Internet text engaging in creative, personally directed secondary speech activity.

According to E. P. Belinskaya (2013) each individual's social network writing is a conversation between the author and other users. Each remark is merely a link in the chain of verbal communication; without dialogical overtones, it would be impossible to grasp the author's idiom. The internet user makes his remark on what would seem to be uncharted communication ground in an effort to align his message with the text's recipient. The preparation of comprehension refers to these actions taken by the blog or website author and the reader.

All of this is very significant to us because it encourages writers of social media comments to adopt language that their intended audience will understand by focusing on a specific addressee.

THE CONCEPT

The idea of Internet communication encompasses not just how the Internet works and develops, but also how it may be used to discuss a wide range of topics. Each user who posts a comment on a social network wants to engage in conversation with others.

The personalization of interactions is a characteristic aspect of interpersonal Internet communication. This exchange is focused on the individual. It is considered that each person using the Internet to communicate understands the individuality of his or her partner, takes into consideration the quirks of his or her emotional state, sense of self, and other distinctive traits, and then anticipates the other person's attention.

In many different fields, including functional-semantic, communicative-pragmatic, psycholinguistic, cognitive, sociolinguistic, literary, integrated, and many others, there is interest in the issue of targeting or orientation of Internet communication. Studies of Internet communication in this field focus on the characterization of the person category, the semantics of personal pronouns and personal verb forms, the imperative, as well as the morphological-syntactic and stylistic characteristics of circulation.

Many linguists are interested in the issue of how Internet text is perceived as a crucial component of a particular kind of Internet communication.

A DIFFERENT KIND OF APPROACH TO COMMUNICATION

According to Popova (2013), as other Internet users interpret the text, the author of a comment on social networks engages in conversation with them. During this conversation, semiotic foundations of the language change, particularly at the level of points of view and relationships due to the pragmatic attitudes of Internet communication; increasingly, attention is given to a particular person who chooses an expression method that is convenient and well-liked by them.

Additionally, you must decide on the "tonality" of your comprehension when speaking online. To preserve unity and purity of understanding, social network users should always select the "key" or "tonality" of their comments. The goal of the conversation between the author of a social media comment and other users is to talk, reach mutual knowledge of the process while retaining one's own perspective and position; evolve, interact; and unite and divide opinions (Gorshkova, 2013).

The presence or lack of constraints on the choice of words to communicate their personal thoughts on a particular occasion or the consensus of supporters of a certain direction created in a particular sector of conflict are distinctive indications of Internet communication (Potemkin, 2012).

The history of the language, the history of this industry of science, technology, or public life in this part of the world, as well as extralinguistic variables, such as these, would seem to be the causes of each specific lexical borrowed word.

According to J. Bagan (2014), distinct, historically and culturally specific ways of phonetic and conceptual expression in different languages - more or less complete, to one degree or another specific - are used to communicate the same concept via Internet conversations.

T. R. Kuzmina (2013) argues that each individual language user participating in Internet communication must be cognizant of their own self-identification as it relates to several aspects of public life, including production, labor, culture, politics, communication, daily life, and others.

According to Katerinich (2013), a broader interpretation of this concept has emerged to replace the understanding of culture as a combination of material and spiritual achievements of civilization. This interpretation is linked to interest in all features of historical, social, and psychological phenomena that are distinctive of a given people, his traditions, social, religious, ethical, aesthetic, and other values, looks, institutes and behavior.

A MATTER OF CULTURE

Every Internet communication language has a strong cultural connection. Given the intricate and indirect nature of its inspiration by other cultural components, all of its structural and functional characteristics should be viewed as manifestations of the culture of the associated language (or ethnic) community. Each person's language-based description of the world reflects the outside world, spiritual life, and human behavior in particular cognitive structures that are realized and organized in their own language categories and forms. The development of different concepts or cognitive structures takes place not only in response to external influences (such as cultural elements or other factors), but also in accordance with internal rules that have an impact on the construction of specific conceptions as holistic formations.

One of the challenges in interacting with netizens who speak a different language or a dialect of the same language is that every language develops its own "linguistic vision of the world."

Different language structures can be used inside each particular language to create a picture of the world, and vice versa, a single structure can be the foundation for the creation and comprehension of a variety of messages. However, native speakers are able to distinguish between the form of expression and the phenomenon or object being represented, so transcending linguistic stereotypes, so the dependence of conveyed thoughts on the manner of their linguistic manifestation is relative and constrained.

Since it applies self-awareness via Internet communication through self-identification, linguistic consciousness as a whole is significant for a nation (or ethnic group, etc.).

CONCLUSION

Web-based communication is now an essential component of modern man's social interactions. The increasing use of various social networks and entertainment options is to blame for this. A person in the modern world today would almost certainly be involved in Internet communication to some extent, making him a netizen. Determining what is intended by Internet communication is necessary in this regard. In interpersonal and mass communication, using a variety of verbal and non-verbal communication techniques, communication is a socially defined process of transmitting and interpreting information. The use of new technologies, such as instant messaging, email use, voice and video transmission via the Internet, has fast supplanted the use of conventional communication methods, such as fax or telephone.

Internet communications refers to communication that uses contemporary Internet technologies, and netizens is the term used to describe its users. Using established protocols for information sharing and presentation, information is transmitted across the Internet in internet communication. Information can be transferred in many different ways over the Internet. Examples include sending voicemails, videos, various papers, instant messages, and other data.

It is indisputable that the Internet is the largest source of information that humanity has ever known. The use of the Internet as a tool for communication as well as a means of learning is made possible by its communication characteristics, such as the speed, accessibility, and ease of communication between users over both short and large distances.

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